

IN MEMORIAM
Prof. Dr Lidija Lazarević (1943 – 2022)

Prof. Dr Lidija Lazarević was born in Sarajevo on 15th July 1943. She completed her primary and secondary education in Sombor (Vojvodina, Serbia), and enrolled in the Faculty of Science, Department of Biology of the University of Belgrade, where she graduated in 1968. In the same year, she was selected for training at the Brain Institute of the Academy of Medical Sciences of the USSR in Moscow. Under the tutorship of Prof. N. Lyubimova, she defended her master thesis, "Structural changes in the corpus geniculatum laterale after deafferentation", in 1973 in Moscow at the Scientific Research Institute of Neurosurgery named after N.N. Burdenko, RAMS, and received a degree of Candidate of Medical Sciences. She was promoted to a Doctor of Medical Sciences at the Faculty of Medicine in Belgrade in 1985, after successfully defending her doctoral dissertation "Evolutionary aspects of the relationship between the striatum and the visual system".

After two years in Moscow (1968-1970), she was employed as an Assistant in Neuromorphology at the Institute of Marine Biology in Kotor, where she remained until her retirement. In addition to working on Institute projects, national and international, Prof. Lidija Lazarević completed a large number of specializations in the country and abroad (USSR, Hungary, England).

During her work at the Institute, Prof. Lazarević held a series of lectures and laboratory exercises for biology students of universities from Sarajevo, Novi Sad, Belgrade, Kragujevac, Skoplje, Priština and Podgorica. She was a mentor for the preparation of several graduate and master's theses and she participated in a large number of summer schools.

From 1995 until her retirement, she was engaged at the Faculty of Science and Mathematics, University of Montenegro, Department of Biology, as a lecturer in "Histology, cytology and embryology".

She was a member of several national and international organizations and societies, including the European Society for Brain and Behavior Research, Yugoslav Society of Physiologists,

Society of Neurobiologists, Biochemical Society of Yugoslavia and Biological society of the Federal Republic of Yugoslavia. In her scientific activity, Prof. Lazarević has published or communicated more than 70 papers in domestic and foreign scientific journals and at symposia.

On 16th July 2022, we were sad to receive the news that our dear colleague Lidija, retired Scientific Advisor – the most senior university scientific position – of the Institute of Marine Biology and professor of the Faculty of Science and Mathematics of the University of Montenegro, passed away. We will remember her as an excellent scientist, professor and colleague. She will also be remembered by generations of students to whom she revealed the most hidden secrets of marine organisms and human physiology at the primary, cellular level.

Vječna joj slava i hvala!

INSTITUTE OF MARINE BIOLOGY KOTOR